

Organ-protective antidiabetic prescriptions in type 2 diabetes – a single institution experience

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Abstract

The aim of this study was to evaluate the antidiabetic therapy during hospitalization, as well as that recommended at discharge from a single university endocrinology clinic for all type 2 diabetes patients admitted over a 12-month period. Of the 464 cases, 345 (74.4%) were emergency admissions and 119 (25.6%) were planned hospitalizations for poor glycemic control. At discharge, one antidiabetic medication was prescribed in 133 patients (28.7%), two in 169 (36.3%), three in 103 (22.2%), and 48 (10.4%) received four or more glucose-lowering agents. Of all patients, 175 (37.7%) were taking sodium-glucose cotransporter 2 inhibitors (SGLT2i), 71 (15.3%) glucagon-like peptide 1 receptor agonists (GLP1-RAs), and 42 (9.1%) both organ-protective classes. Among patients with concomitant cardiovascular disease, chronic kidney disease, or both (n = 300; 64.7%), SGLT2i was prescribed in 150 (50.0%), GLP1-RA in 51 (17.0%), and both in 34 individuals (11.3%). Our results indicate that more than half of the patients at cardio-renal risk (55.7%) received at least one organ-protective medication.

Keywords

diabetes type 2, cardiovascular and renal risk, GLP1-receptor agonists, SGLT2 inhibitors

Introduction

Modern clinical guidelines for the treatment of type 2 diabetes offer a holistic approach that places the diabetic patient at the center (Davies et al. 2022b). This comprehensive care includes glycemic control, weight management, cardiorenal protection, and management of cardiovascular risk factors (Davies et al. 2022b). The holistic approach pertains to a newly recognized disorder, introduced by the American Heart Association (AHA) in October 2023, defined as cardiovascular-kidney-metabolic (CKM) syndrome (Ndumele

et al. 2023). This syndrome represents a health condition linked to obesity, type 2 diabetes mellitus, chronic kidney disease (CKD), and cardiovascular disease (CVD), which encompasses heart failure, atrial fibrillation, coronary heart disease, stroke, and peripheral arterial disease (Ndumele et al. 2023). The interrelated pathophysiology of metabolic, renal, and cardiovascular disturbances emphasizes the necessity for pleiotropic medications that address all these conditions and possess the potential to alter the progression of CKM syndrome in both its initial stages and in stages 3 and 4 (Ndumele et al. 2023; Ferdinand 2024).

Given that certain glucose-lowering medications have demonstrated organ-protective benefits in randomized clinical trials (RCTs), the present therapeutic choices for individuals with type 2 diabetes are progressively shaped by the presence of chronic kidney disease, heart failure, and atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease.

SGLT2 inhibitors block the sodium-glucose cotransporter 2 (SGLT2) in the proximal renal tubules. This leads to reduced glucose reabsorption and increased urinary glucose excretion—up to 80 g/daily or approximately equal to 280 kcal/daily loss. Initially developed for glycemic control in type 2 diabetes, SGLT2 inhibitors have demonstrated additional benefits and are now also indicated for heart failure management and delaying chronic kidney disease progression, regardless of the presence or absence of diabetes (Heerspink et al. 2020; Anker et al. 2021; Volpe and Pedicino 2022; The EMPA-KIDNEY Collaborative Group et al. 2023). Further advantages of this glucose-lowering class include a reduction in serum uric acid and moderate weight reduction (Pratama et al. 2022; Yang et al. 2025).

GLP1-RAs (glucagon-like peptide 1 receptor agonists) act by increasing glucose-induced insulin secretion, improving beta-cell preservation, decreasing glucagon secretion in both hyperglycemia and normoglycemia, and delaying gastric emptying to prevent postprandial hyperglycemia, thereby reducing food intake. Moreover, GLP1-RAs also act at the hypothalamus, promoting satiety and consequently reducing food intake. Initially developed as antidiabetic medications, some GLP1-RAs are currently registered as weight loss treatments regardless of diabetes status. Certain incretin-based formulations have demonstrated significant reductions in the risk of cardiovascular events, as shown in RCTs such as LEADER, SUSTAIN-6, PIONEER 6, REWIND, and HARMONY (Hernandez et al. 2018; Mann et al. 2018; Gerstein et al. 2019; Husain et al. 2019; Frías et al. 2021). Additionally, recent data indicate that GLP1-RAs have favorable effects in patients with metabolic dysfunction-associated steatohepatitis (MASH) (Sanyal et al. 2025).

Why organ protection in type 2 diabetes?

The recent 2025 American Diabetes Association Standards of Care recommend the use of medications that lower the risk of both cardiovascular and kidney complications for all adults with type 2 diabetes who either have established or are at high risk for atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease (ASCVD), heart failure (HF), and/or chronic kidney disease (CKD) (American Diabetes Association Professional Practice Committee 2024). For patients with ASCVD, the clinician can choose between GLP-1R agonists or SGLT2 inhibitors, and later on a combination of both classes may be considered if glycemic targets are not reached (American Diabetes Association Professional Practice Committee 2024). For diabetic patients with concomitant heart failure, both with reduced or preserved ejection fraction,

SGLT2 inhibitors are the preferred choice based on results from the EMPAREG trial, as well as the EMPEROR and DAPA-HF clinical trial programs (McMurray et al. 2019; Anker et al. 2021). For patients with type 2 diabetes who have chronic kidney disease, either an SGLT2 inhibitor or a GLP-1 RA should be used both for glycemic control and to slow CKD progression in terms of reducing albuminuria and eGFR deterioration. Following the results of the FLOW study, which demonstrated risk reduction in kidney outcomes in patients with type 2 diabetes and CKD, multiple clinical trials are currently investigating the kidney-protective effects of different incretin-based formulations (single, double, or triple agonists). A further combination of an SGLT2 inhibitor and GLP-1 RA is also possible when target glycosylated hemoglobin levels are not reached by patients with diabetes and CKD (American Diabetes Association Professional Practice Committee 2024).

Thus, SGLT2 inhibitors and GLP1-RAs are prioritized as “strategic” for organ (kidney and heart) protection in comparison with other antidiabetic medications such as metformin, pioglitazone, DPP-4 inhibitors, sulfonylureas, and insulin. An additional advantage of these “strategic” classes is their low to negligible risk of hypoglycemia.

Notwithstanding the clinical guidelines outlined for the management of antidiabetic therapy in patients with cardiovascular and/or renal conditions, the utilization of the recommended “strategic” drug classes remains suboptimal. This discrepancy can be attributed in part to clinical inertia, as well as to the high costs associated with these medications, restrictions in reimbursement policies, and their potential side effects (Almigbal et al. 2023; Peneva et al. 2024; Mitkova et al. 2025). Given that both SGLT2 inhibitors and GLP-1 receptor agonists (GLP-1RAs) are relatively costly, typically only one of these can be reimbursed for antidiabetic treatment. SGLT2 inhibitors may receive partial reimbursement for the management of heart failure or chronic kidney disease, contingent upon a prescription from a cardiologist or nephrologist, respectively. Consequently, numerous Bulgarian patients diagnosed with diabetes alongside cardiovascular or renal diseases are prescribed a GLP-1RA as part of their antidiabetic regimen (in conjunction with other oral medications or insulin) and an SGLT2 inhibitor for heart failure or chronic kidney disease. A recent pharmacoeconomic evaluation conducted in Bulgaria indicated that public expenditure on SGLT2 inhibitors peaked during the COVID-19 pandemic and continued thereafter, a trend that can be rationalized by the multiple indications for prescribing this class of drugs (Mitkova et al. 2025).

The aim of our study was to evaluate the antidiabetic therapy during hospitalization, as well as that recommended at discharge from a single university-based endocrinology clinic for all patients with type 2 diabetes admitted over a 12-month period. A secondary objective was to elucidate the percentage of patients treated with one or two organ-protective medications.

Materials and methods

This retrospective observational study was conducted, following ethical approval, in the Clinic of Endocrinology and Metabolic Diseases, University Hospital “St. Marina” Varna (a tertiary referral center), using electronic medical records. The study encompassed a total of 464 patients over the age of 18 diagnosed with type 2 diabetes who were admitted to the clinic during a one-year period, specifically from April 1, 2024, to March 31, 2025. Patients were categorized based on the reason for admission, which included emergency cases due to acute diabetes decompensation or planned hospitalizations for inadequate glycemic control. They were also classified according to their HbA1c levels. Information was collected regarding the duration of diabetes, the presence of microvascular and macrovascular complications, and any concomitant diseases, with particular emphasis on heart failure, cardiovascular conditions, and chronic kidney disease. The average duration of hospital stay was 3.9 (± 0.6) days, and good clinical practices to modify antidiabetic treatment in accordance with international guidelines were implemented whenever feasible. A detailed analysis of the therapy provided at hospital discharge was conducted, including recommendations for both the patient and the attending physician. Descriptive statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS, version 19. Categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages. Numerical variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) for normally distributed data and as median \pm interquartile range (IQR) for non-normally distributed data.

Results

Out of the 464 patients with type 2 diabetes admitted to the clinic over the course of one year, 345 individuals (74.4%) were hospitalized on an emergency basis, while the remaining 119 patients (25.6%) were admitted electively due to inadequate glycemic control (see Table 1). The study population consisted of 191 men (41.2%) and 273 women (58.8%), indicating a higher prevalence of female patients among those hospitalized for type 2 diabetes.

Glycosylated hemoglobin value was $\leq 7.0\%$ in only 61 patients, between 7.01–8.99% in 103, and $\geq 9.0\%$ in 300 study participants (Table 1). The mean duration of diabetes was 12.3 years (± 9.4). Of the studied patients, 31.0% ($n = 144$) had a disease duration of less than 5 years, 17.5% ($n = 81$) had 6–10 years, 12.3% ($n = 57$) had 11–15 years, and 39.2% ($n = 182$) had diabetes for 16 or more years (Table 1).

The mean age of the participants was 64.9 (± 13.5) years, with the majority (37.5%, $n = 174$) aged over 70 years and the minority aged 18–30 years (2.2%, $n = 10$). The other age subgroups were as follows: 31–40 years (2.8%, $n = 13$), 41–50 years (9.1%, $n = 42$), 51–60 years (21.3%, $n = 99$), and 61–70 years (27.2%, $n = 126$), as illustrated in Table 1.

At discharge, glucose-lowering therapy with one medication was prescribed and recommended as home treatment in 133 patients (28.7%), two antidiabetic medications

in 169 (36.3%), three medications in 103 (22.2%), and 48 (10.4%) received four or more antidiabetic agents (Table 2). Of all patients, 175 (37.7%) were taking SGLT2 inhibitors, 71 (15.3%) GLP1-RAs, and 42 (9.1%) both organ-protective classes (Table 2). Temporary or long-term insulin treatment was used in 310 of the included subjects (66.8%), especially in emergency admissions as a measure to overcome glucotoxicity. Metformin was included in the treatment regimen of 244 patients (52.6%), sulfonylurea in 79 cases (17.0%), DPP-4 inhibitors in 66 (14.2%), thiazolidinediones in 2 (0.4%), and meglitinides in a single patient (0.2%).

Among patients considered at risk (ASCVD, CKD, and HF) ($n = 300$; 64.7%), an SGLT2 inhibitor was administered to 150 individuals (50.0%), while 51 cases (17.0%) were prescribed a GLP1-RA. Additionally, 16 patients (5.3%) were advised to initiate GLP1-RA treatment after a period of 3–6 months, in accordance with the drug reimbursement criteria (Table 3).

A combination of a GLP1-RA and an SGLT2i was initiated in 34 individuals (11.3%). The prescribed representatives of the SGLT2i and GLP1-RA classes are detailed in Table 3, as well as Figs 1, 2.

Among the 164 patients who did not have cardiac or kidney conditions, 25 individuals (15.2%) were treated with an SGLT2i, 20 cases (12.2%) were given a GLP1-RA, and 6 patients (3.6%) received both types of medication.

Table 1. Clinical characteristics of patients with type 2 diabetes admitted to the clinic between April 2024 and March 2025.

	Patients (n)	Age in years, mean (\pm) SD	Frequency (%)
Sex			
Male	191	61.2 (± 13.9)	41%
Female	273	67.4 (± 12.6)	59%
Total	464	64.9 (± 13.5)	100%
Age groups (years old)			
18–30	10	25.1 (± 3.6)	2.1%
31–40	13	36.8 (± 2.3)	2.8%
41–50	42	46.4 (± 2.8)	9.1%
51–60	99	56.1 (± 3.0)	21.3%
61–70	126	66.1 (± 3.1)	27.2%
70–99	174	77.8 (± 5.0)	37.5%
Duration of Diabetes (years)			
0–5	144		31.0%
6–10	81		17.5%
11–15	57		12.3%
16–99	182		39.2%
Admission			
Planned	119		25.6%
Emergency	345		74.4%
HbA1C Categories			
≤ 7.00	62		13.4%
7.01–8.99	102		22.0%
≥ 9.0	300		64.6%
Comorbidities			
ASCVD	262		56.5%
CKD	92		19.8%
HF	157		33.8%
ASCVD and/or CKD and/or HF	300		64.7%

Table 2. Distribution of patients by number and type of antidiabetic medications at hospital discharge.

Number of antidiabetic drugs at discharge	
No therapy (diet and lifestyle changes)	2.4% (n = 11)
Monotherapy	28.7% (n = 133)
Double therapy	36.3% (n = 169)
Triple therapy	22.2% (n = 103)
Four or more antidiabetic medications	10.4% (n = 48)
Class of antidiabetic drugs at discharge	
Metformin	52.6% (n = 244)
Sulfonylurea	17.0% (n = 79)
SGLT2 inhibitor	37.7% (n = 175)
GLP-1 RA	15.30% (n = 71)
SGLT2 inhibitor + GLP-1 RA	9.1% (n = 42)
Recommended future GLP-1 RA initiation	5.4% (n = 25)
Insulin	66.8% (n = 310)
DPP-4 inhibitors	14.2% (n = 66)
Thiazolidinediones	0.4% (n = 2)
Meglitinides	0.2% (n = 1)

Table 3. Type of organ-protective therapy given to patients with ASCVD, CKD, or HF (n = 300).

SGLT2 inhibitors	50.0% (n = 150)
Empagliflozin	21.3% (n = 64)
Dapagliflozin	27.7% (n = 83)
Canagliflozin	1.0% (n = 3)
GLP-1 RA	17.0% (n = 51)
Semaglutide	4.7% (n = 14)
Liraglutide	9.0% (n = 27)
Lixisenatide	2.7% (n = 8)
Dulaglutide	0.6% (n = 2)
Combined SGLT2 i + GLP-1 RA	11.3% (n = 34)
Recommendation for future GLP-1 RA	5.3% (n = 16)

Discussion

The majority of our patients were admitted due to poor glycemic control, with half of the cohort having HbA1c \geq 9%. This corresponds to high or very high blood glucose levels requiring urgent hospitalization in most cases. The dominant percentage of admissions was among patients over the age of 70 years (37.5%), reflecting the longer duration of diabetes as well as social gaps in the care of elderly individuals.

Our single-center data provide information about the real-world prescribing patterns of organ-protective antidiabetic medications at hospital discharge in patients with type 2 diabetes, emphasizing individuals with ASCVD, CKD, and HF. According to the study design, we consider the therapy at dehospitalization as most indicative of our attempt to implement changes in glucose-lowering treatment according to international recommendations, on one hand, and to address side effects and contraindications in each individual case, on the other.

Our findings indicate that over half of the patients (n = 167; 55.7%) were discharged with at least one organ-protective medication, predominantly SGLT2 inhibitors and, to a lesser extent, GLP-1 receptor agonists. Nevertheless, in order to meet the needs of the majority of patients with cardiovascular disease (CVD) or chronic kidney disease

Figure 2. GLP1-RA therapy in patients with cardiovascular or chronic kidney disease or heart failure (n = 300).

(CKD), as outlined by international clinical guidelines, it remains essential to address the issue of clinical inertia (Davies et al. 2022a).

In the whole studied group, 2.5 times more patients received SGLT2 inhibitors compared to GLP-1 RAs. Both medication classes are recommended for organ protection and as part of the holistic approach to diabetic patients endorsed by international diabetes management guidelines. Logically, the question arises: why was one prescribed more frequently than the other? This could be explained by the specific reimbursement criteria for different antidiabetic classes in Bulgaria and their relatively high cost. At the time of the study, patients with HF or CKD were eligible for reimbursement of SGLT2 inhibitors without the need to meet other diabetes control criteria. In comparison, the reimbursement of GLP-1 RAs required a diabetes duration of more than 3 months and unsatisfactory glycemic control on monotherapy or combination therapy (measured by glycated hemoglobin levels). This is not in line with guidelines proposing organ protection for at-risk patients regardless of glycemic control. The limitations of the reimbursement policy often result in intensification of

antidiabetic therapy with other classes (not organ-protective) and delayed use of disease-modifying agents, especially GLP-1 RAs. Another consideration is patients' fear of injections and reluctance to initiate treatment, as most GLP-1 RAs available on the market are injectable, except for the oral form of semaglutide.

In a survey conducted in Spain regarding the obstacles and strategies for the effective utilization of GLP-1 receptor agonists (RAs) in individuals with type 2 diabetes who are at high cardiovascular risk or have established cardiovascular disease, Botana López et al. (2024) pinpointed therapeutic inertia as a significant limitation related to physicians, while identifying administrative requirements as the primary barrier associated with the healthcare process.

Recently, Yun et al. (2025) from the United States devised and evaluated a quality improvement initiative aimed at enhancing the utilization of SGLT2 inhibitors and GLP-1 RAs among patients diagnosed with type 2 diabetes and atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease (ASCVD), CKD, and/or HF. This initiative, implemented at the Veterans Affairs Ann Arbor Healthcare System, encompassed strategies that targeted clinician and pharmacist coaching, provided feedback to healthcare providers, and identified patients who were at risk but not receiving treatment with these two classes of medications. Following the intervention, the rates of prescriptions for SGLT2 inhibitors and GLP-1 RAs experienced a significant increase, with this rise occurring at a rate 8% faster than the national average (Yun et al. 2025).

The tendency for prescribing SGLT2i over GLP-1 RA was similarly reported in a recent study in Switzerland showing that 29.4% of patients received SGLT2i at discharge compared to 8.7% receiving GLP-1 agonists (Meier et al. 2024). The same pattern is seen in a study from the USA, where in 2019 about 15% of the included patients received an SGLT2i, while 10% were on a GLP-1 RA (Gay et al. 2023). Another article from Australia indicates that about 2 times more patients receive SGLT2i in contrast to GLP-1 RA (Lin et al. 2023).

In our cohort, 34 (11.3%) of the high-risk individuals started a combination therapy with both SGLT2i and GLP-1 RA. In a recent analysis by Wright et al. (2022) in England and Wales, the SGLT2i/GLP-1RA combination was nominally associated with lower odds of primary end points (MACCE) than SGLT2 inhibitors or GLP-1RAs alone in patients with ASCVD, HF, or CKD.

Taking into account the median age of the population under investigation (64.9 years, $SD \pm 13.5$), there may be apprehensions regarding the detrimental impacts of stringent glycemic management, including hypoglycemia, fall risk, and heightened mortality, as indicated by various studies (McCoy et al. 2016; Lega et al. 2021). Nevertheless, organ-protective medications do not affect the risk of hypoglycemia; however, their administration is significantly affected by the existence of contraindications (such as active urinary infections for SGLT2i and pancreatitis for GLP-1 RA).

One of the strengths of the study is the up-to-date real-world data (from April 2024 to March 2025) used for

the analysis. Additionally, it stands out as one of the few studies investigating prescription trends during that time period in Bulgaria.

The primary limitation of this study lies in its retrospective, single-center design. Additionally, the data are restricted to inpatient cases, excluding outpatients. There is a lack of information regarding variables such as patient income, health insurance status, or mental health, all of which could influence the decision-making process for antidiabetic treatment. Furthermore, being a tertiary referral center may correlate with a patient population that presents with more severe or complex cases, thereby influencing therapy selection. It would be beneficial to conduct a follow-up on this cohort concerning treatment adherence in outpatient settings. Moreover, a national prospective study focusing on the outpatient prescription of organ-protective glucose-lowering medications is warranted, which could be compared with both university-affiliated clinics and international trends.

Conclusion

The majority of hospitalized patients have significantly impaired glycemic control ($HbA1c \geq 9.0\%$), often requiring temporary or long-term insulin therapy. On the other hand, the glucocentric approach has been displaced by a broader cardio-renal-metabolic strategy, opening the possibility to prioritize disease-modifying medications. Our results show that a significant proportion (55.7%) of patients at cardio-renal risk receive at least one organ-protective medication, more commonly an SGLT2i. However, more than 44% of diabetic patients with ASCVD, CKD, or HF remain uncovered with these “strategic” classes of antidiabetics. The limitations on reimbursement, clinical inertia, and existing contraindications may contribute to this issue. To gain a comprehensive understanding of the prescription trends for glucose-lowering medications in Bulgaria, prospective multicenter studies that include outpatients and follow-up data are essential.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

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Author contributions

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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